

Laminar burning velocity and unburnt temperature: Comparative analysis across a broad temperature range of atmospheric NH₃+H₂ flames

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ABSTRACT

Ammonia (NH₃) emerges as a promising carbon-free fuel, necessitating an understanding of its fundamental combustion properties, particularly the laminar burning velocity (S_L), at very high unburnt temperatures (T_u). Despite this need, a consensus on the relationship between S_L and T_u across a broad temperature range has not yet been established. This study investigated the S_L vs. T_u relationship from 298 K to above 800 K, analyzing both literature data and simulation results for 40%H₂+60%NH₃+air flames at 1 atm. Seven kinetic models were used in the simulations, among which the models from Shrestha, Stagni, Han, NUIG, and KAUST accurately reproduced the experimental data within uncertainty limits, making them suitable for investigating S_L vs. T_u relationship. The analysis revealed that no tested correlation perfectly captures the S_L vs. T_u relationship across the entire temperature range with their originally defined constants, because the overall activation energy of the global one-step reaction is indeed increasing rapidly with T_u . In addition, the much lower reaction sensitivities of the temperature dependence coefficient than S_L , along with the same effects of elevated temperature and oxygen enrichment on model validations, were found to be valid for temperatures up to 850 K in these simulations, consistent with those previously identified for $T_u < 500$ K conditions. Reaction sensitivities were also calculated for the overall activation energy, which exhibits significantly stronger temperature dependence than S_L , thus more effective for identifying reactions requiring adjustment for improving predictions across wide unburnt temperature ranges. Based on these findings, a feasible strategy was proposed for future investigation of the laminar burning velocities with broad unburnt temperature range, helping with relevant applications.

Novelty and Significance statement

The novelty of this research is the comprehensive analysis of the relationship between the laminar burning velocity (S_L) and unburnt temperature (T_u) for NH₃+H₂ flames, spanning a range up to 800 K. It reveals that existing correlations, with their originally defined constants, fail to precisely capture the S_L vs. T_u dependence across the wide temperature range, attributing this to a rise in the overall activation energy with increasing T_u . This work is important as it proposed a feasible strategy for future investigation of the laminar burning velocities with broad unburnt temperature range, i.e., (1) substituting high T_u measurements with oxygen enrichment experiments, (2) validating the models using the experimental data or model updating considering the sensitivities of overall activation energy, and (3) simulating the S_L directly or fitting parameters to correlations for interpolation/extrapolation,

reducing computational costs.

1. Introduction

Ammonia (NH₃) is a promising carbon-free fuel, and its fundamental flame properties, particularly the laminar burning velocity (S_L), have caught great attention in the literature. Laminar burning velocity is a key parameter that describes flame propagation, providing a foundation for understanding more complex flame characteristics such as flammability limits and turbulent flame speeds. It is also crucial for validating and optimizing kinetic models. Consequently, numerous measurements have been conducted to obtain S_L data under various conditions, including different fuel blends, equivalence ratios, oxidation environments, unburnt temperatures, and pressures [1]. Alongside this, kinetic models have proliferated, with many being continuously updated to incorporate new kinetic findings and better reproduce experimental

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data [1,2].

The importance of NH_3 S_L at very high unburnt temperatures is widely acknowledged, especially considering the prevalence of engines and gas turbines in large-scale applications. However, conducting high-temperature S_L measurements poses significant challenges. Besides challenges in gas handling at high temperatures, a fundamental issue is the intrinsic flame instabilities [3] that can distort the required smooth flame shapes, such as the spherical shape needed in the spherical flame method and the flat flames required in the heat flux method. Even with advanced techniques to overcome high-temperature instabilities, NH_3 is prone to thermal decomposition [4], which can be accelerated by the catalytic effects of metals involved, for example, in iron-containing chambers. If the heating from room temperature is not sufficiently rapid, the actual unburnt NH_3 fuel may have already been converted to $\text{NH}_3+\text{H}_2+\text{N}_2$ mixtures, which exhibit significantly larger laminar burning velocities [5–7].

Due to the aforementioned reasons, the majority of available laminar burning velocity data for NH_3 and NH_3+H_2 mixtures have been obtained with unburnt mixture temperatures below 500 K, such as those in [8–12], summarised recently by Szanthoffer et al. [1,2]. In these studies and related numerical works employing various models, a power-law correlation, Eq. (1), is commonly used to describe S_L 's dependence on unburnt mixture temperature T_u , where the subscript 0 denotes a reference state, often 298 K, and α is a temperature-independent constant influenced by mixture compositions. This empirical correlation, introduced by Dugger and colleagues in the 1950s [13,14], has been extensively applied to describe the S_L vs. T_u dependences of various fuels [15], with several formats further detailing how the fitted α varies with equivalence ratio ϕ , such as $\alpha = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2\phi$ [16] and $\alpha = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2\phi + \alpha_3\phi^2$ [17,18]. Eq. (1) is often used to analyze the consistency of experimental data obtained for the same mixture but at different T_u , as exemplified for many fuels by Konnov et al. [8,15]. This, however, does not imply that α is T_u -independent because its variation over extended range of temperatures is also well established. For example, Alekseev et al. [19] demonstrated that for $\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$ and $\text{H}_2 + \text{air}$ flames the power exponents α monotonously increase with T_u over 300 – 800 K, yet their variation is different for different equivalence ratios. Based on the assumption of a global one-step reaction, our previous work [20] suggested that α depends on the unburnt temperature range, as shown in Eq. (2), which is also correlated to the overall activation energy E_a of the global one-step reaction through Eq. (3), with T_{ad} representing the adiabatic flame temperature. For NH_3 flames and mixtures with H_2 , methane, methanol, and ethanol up to 448 K unburnt temperature, the E_a and x in Eq. (3) were assumed and confirmed to be independent of T_u [8,11]. It should be noted that a T_u -independent α can be viewed as a specific value of $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$, averaged over the investigated range. While the fitted α , E_a , and x could potentially extrapolate S_L values above 500 K, possibly refined with model predictions, the accuracy and applicability of Eqs. (1)–(3) remain unconfirmed without corresponding measurements.

$$S_L/S_{L0} = (T_u/T_{u0})^\alpha \quad (1)$$

$$\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u} = \ln(S_L/S_{L0})/\ln(T_u/T_{u0}) \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u} = E_a/2R \cdot X + x, \quad X = \left(\frac{1}{T_{ad0}} - \frac{1}{T_{ad}}\right) / \ln(T_u/T_{u0}) \quad (3)$$

The only NH_3 and NH_3+H_2 S_L measurements with $T_u > 500$ K were reported very recently by Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21,22] and Shawnam et al. [23], reaching maximum unburnt temperatures of 820 K and 725 K, respectively. These studies employed novel techniques of spherical flames in shock tube [21,22] and flat flames in externally heated diverging channel [23]. The studies present differing views on the S_L vs. T_u relationship. Shawnam et al. [23], like many < 500 K studies, used a T_u -independent α and demonstrated its dependence on unburnt mixture composition. In contrast, Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21, 22] suggested a unique S_L vs. T_u correlation, Eq. (4), called the

“non-Arrhenius model”, introducing a correction factor $\exp\left(\frac{T_u - T_{u0}}{T_{exp}}\right)$ to the standard power-law correlation Eq. (1). This model was initially proposed by the same group for measuring the S_L of various fuels at high T_u using shock waves [24,25], with T_{exp} and α_{NA} being fitted values independent of the T_u range. Figueroa-Labastida et al. emphasized that the non-Arrhenius model better describes elevated temperature measurements, significantly reducing the deviation between fitted and experimental results, for instance, reducing the largest deviation for NH_3 S_L at 565 K from 14.6% using Eq. (1) to 6.6% using Eq. (4) [22]. Transforming Eq. (4) yields Eq. (5), where a temperature-dependent $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ is considered influenced by α_{NA} , $1/T_{exp}$, and $(T_u - T_{u0})/\ln(T_u/T_{u0}^0)$. The intercept and slope of $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ vs. $(T_u - T_{u0})/\ln(T_u/T_{u0}^0)$ can be linearly fitted to determine α_{NA} and $1/T_{exp}$, respectively. It is noted that Eq. (5) resembles Eq. (3), both featuring a parameter that describes the influence of the T_u range, i.e., $\left(\frac{1}{T_{ad0}} - \frac{1}{T_{ad}}\right)/\ln(T_u/T_{u0})$ in Eq. (3) and $(T_u - T_{u0})/\ln(T_u/T_{u0}^0)$ in Eq. (5), accompanied by fitted parameters independent of T_u . This similarity raises the question of whether Eq. (5) could also be applied to high-temperature conditions with acceptable accuracy, which would be advantageous since Eq. (3) involves the fitting parameters with physical meanings related to global one-step reaction characteristics, whereas those in Eq. (5) are purely empirical. Additionally, the varying correlations suggested by different studies prompt the question of which is more suitable for evaluating S_L under industrial conditions, particularly with a large T_u span.

$$S_L/S_{L0} = (T_u/T_{u0})^{\alpha_{NA}} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{T_u - T_{u0}}{T_{exp}}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u} = \alpha_{NA} + 1/T_{exp}(T_u - T_{u0})/\ln(T_u/T_{u0}^0) \quad (5)$$

In addition to the correlation, other features have been identified in studies below 500 K regarding the S_L vs. T_u dependence. Our recent analysis of fuel-rich $\text{NH}_3+\text{N}_2+\text{O}_2$ flames revealed that the effects of elevated temperature and oxygen enrichment are the same for the kinetic model validations [26]. This study also identified similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities, suggesting that S_L measurements with elevated T_u , challenging in experiments, could be replaced by more feasible measurements with increased oxygen enrichment ratios to check the reliability of kinetic models. It is intriguing and beneficial to determine if these similarities persist for laminar burning velocities above 500 K, which could be achieved now thanks to the works from Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21,22] and Shawnam et al. [23], where the availability of high- T_u experimental data enables the evaluation of various models, facilitating in-depth kinetic analysis.

Based on the background above, the aims of the present study are (1) to compare S_L vs. T_u correlations across a broad range of unburnt temperatures to determine their suitability for relevant applications and (2) to find out if the same effects of elevated temperature and oxygen enrichment on model validations as well as similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities are also valid for high- T_u conditions. To achieve these, simulations using multiple models were carried out along with analysis, before which the evaluation of the high- T_u data uncertainties from the literature measurements were also performed.

2. Numerical setup

Simulations were carried out using the Chemkin II [27] software for all the present experimental conditions. Seven detailed models were adopted, namely Han [28], Stagni [29], Konnov (version released by Chen et al. [30]), Shrestha [12], KAUST (version released by Zhang et al. [31]), Zhou [32], and NUIG (version released by Zhu et al. [33]). These selections were based on their wide usage in literature for modelling the ammonia combustion characteristics including the laminar burning

velocity, in addition to their largely different reaction paths and predictions summarized by Szanthoffer et al. [1,2], thus avoiding model-specific conclusions.

In simulations, radiation heat losses were accounted for as detailed in [8]. The parameters CURV and GRAD were set both at 0.01, with the Soret effect and multi-component transport considered. In most cases, the number of grid points achieved was higher than 1000. It should be noted that the present grids are more refined than most of the former studies of ammonia such as [26,34], to reduce the simulation data scatters and in turn the numerical noise in the derivations of α and other coefficients.

3. Literature data above 500 K and uncertainties

As outlined in the Introduction, experimental data for NH_3 or NH_3+H_2 flames with $T_u > 500$ K are scarce, with the only sources being Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21,22] and Shawnam et al. [23]. The repeated conditions in these studies involved 1 atm $40\%\text{H}_2+60\%\text{NH}_3$ flames with equivalence ratios of 0.8, 1.0, and 1.2 [21,23], which form the basis of the present analysis and comparison.

Figueroa-Labastida et al. S_L data [21], were not obtained in the air but were scaled from "airgon" (79%Ar+21%O₂) measurements through Eq. (6), where $(S_{L,\text{air}}/S_{L,\text{airgon}})_{\text{sim}}$ is a scaling factor averaged from simulation results of various models [21]. Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21] referred to their previous work by Zheng et al. [24] to prove the validity of this scaling method, where the scaling factors from four models scatter within 1.5% for propane flames. This scatter was suggested to be propagated as an uncertainty source to $S_{L,\text{air}}$ uncertainty [24], in addition to the uncertainty from $S_{L,\text{airgon}}$ measurements, as shown in Eq. (7), where the scaling factor is denoted as ζ for simplicity. Eq. (7) indicates that the relative uncertainty in $S_{L,\text{air}}$ should always be greater than that of $S_{L,\text{airgon}}$, however, the reverse was found for some conditions in the Supplementary Material (SM) of Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21]. For instance, at $\phi = 1.2$ and $T_u = 820$ K ($40\%\text{H}_2+60\%\text{NH}_3$), the reported relative uncertainties of the scaled air and measured airgon mixtures were 5.73% and 6.57%, respectively, suggesting potential errors in data processing in [21]. Consequently, $S_{L,\text{air}}$ and $\Delta S_{L,\text{air}}$ were re-evaluated in the present study based on the directly-measured $S_{L,\text{airgon}}$ and $\Delta S_{L,\text{airgon}}$ [21]. The scaling factors ζ , not found in [21], were averaged using the seven models listed in Section 2, i.e. with more models employed than [21]. The maximum deviations among the modelling results from the averaged ζ values represented $\Delta\zeta$. The re-evaluation results are detailed in the SM file of this study, showing differences of up to 11.9% compared to Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21], although the uncertainties overlap under most conditions. It is noteworthy that the maximum $\Delta\zeta/\zeta$ calculated using the seven models for NH_3+H_2 flames is 6.2%, implying that the maximum scatter range among the models could reach 12.4%. This value is significantly higher than the 1.5% reported for propane flames [24], indicating that the scaling factor is less reliable for NH_3+H_2 flames, leading to larger uncertainties.

$$S_{L,\text{air}} = (S_{L,\text{air}}/S_{L,\text{airgon}})_{\text{sim}} \times S_{L,\text{airgon}} \quad (6)$$

$$\left(\frac{\Delta S_{L,\text{air}}}{S_{L,\text{air}}}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\Delta S_{L,\text{airgon}}}{S_{L,\text{airgon}}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta\zeta}{\zeta}\right)^2 \quad (7)$$

In the study by Shawnam et al. [23], inconsistencies are noted between the S_L experimental data presented in the manuscript figures and the Supplementary Material. The manuscript figures and their accompanying explanations indicate H_2 blending ratios of 20%, 30%, and 40% in the NH_3+H_2 mixtures, whereas S_L data in their SM list 22.5% and 37.2% mixtures, with also more significant scattering. To address this, all discussions regarding [23] in this study are based on the data from the manuscript, which have been digitized along with their associated uncertainties.

4. Result and discussion

4.1. S_L and α coefficient

Fig. 1 shows the laminar burning velocities of $40\%\text{H}_2+60\%\text{NH}_3$ +air flames at 1 atm across a broad range of unburnt temperatures from 298 K to 923 K, with panels (a) to (c) corresponding to equivalence ratios $\phi = 0.8, 1.0,$ and $1.2,$ respectively. In each panel, the data were plotted as $\ln S_L$ vs. $\ln T_u$, in accordance with Eqs. (1)-(2), to assess whether the α coefficient remains constant across various T_u ranges. Experimental data for T_u below 500 K in Fig. 1 are sourced from Jin et al. [10] and Lhuillier et al. [9] obtained using the spherical flame method, as well as from our previous work by Wang et al. [11] obtained using the heat flux method. Data up to 800 K are from Shawnam et al. [23] and Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21]. The uncertainties in $\ln S_L$ of the experimental data, represented by y-axis error bars, were propagated from the S_L uncertainties (ΔS_L) as $\Delta S_L/S_L$. For the Figueroa-Labastida et al. data [21], both the original and present scaled datasets were displayed, with significant differences found at $\phi = 1.2$. It is noted from Fig. 1 that the literature datasets align within uncertainty ranges for overlapping conditions, with the exception of the 493 K data from Jin et al. [10], which deviates from the trend. Simulation results were calculated with a 5 K step. All models except the Konnov model [30] and the Zhou model [32] accurately reproduce the experimental data within uncertainties. The Konnov model and Zhou model, respectively, overestimate and underestimate slightly the data at $\phi = 1.2$ across different unburnt temperatures. This observation is not surprising as the Shrestha, Stagni, Han, NUIG, and KAUST models have been found to be highly accurate for S_L predictions across all available experimental data [1,2]. Consequently, the simulation results, particularly those from the Shrestha, Stagni, Han, NUIG, and KAUST models, are suitable for investigating the S_L dependence on T_u , exhibiting less deviation compared to the experimental data.

Simulation results in Fig. 1 demonstrate that $\ln S_L$ increases approximately linearly with $\ln T_u$ across the broad range of temperatures investigated, with the R^2 value of the linear fit exceeding 0.9959, irrespective of the model used and the equivalence ratio ϕ . However, upon closer examination of the residuals at the top of each panel, which represent the differences between the linear fit and the simulated $\ln S_L$ values, the $\ln S_L$ vs. $\ln T_u$ curve deviates from linearity at both ends, where results from various models show good agreement. This observation suggests that the α coefficient is not constant and should increase with T_u given a specific T_{u0} , as indicated by the trend of the residuals. This conclusion, derived from fitting residuals, aligns with findings from previous works [8,11,19] and Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21], though the mentioned works analyzed $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ and directly fitted various correlations instead of checking the fitting residuals of $\ln S_L$ vs. $\ln T_u$ curves. The variations in α coefficient across T_u were explained in our previous works [8,11] and Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21] through Eq. (3) and Eq. (5), respectively, as the terms $X = \left(\frac{1}{T_{ad0}} - \frac{1}{T_{ad}}\right) / \ln(T_u/T_{u0})$ and $(T_u - T_{u0}) / \ln(T_u/T_{u0}^0)$ both increase with T_u . However, from the following analysis, it could be found that the other terms in these equations are also T_u -dependent.

To compare the correlation adopted by Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21] (Eq. (5)) and that used in our previous works [8,11] (Eq. (3)), the $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ values were derived from Eq. (2) using both experimental and simulated datasets in Fig. 1, with the reference state T_{u0} set at 298 K. For the Figueroa-Labastida et al. data [21] lacking 298 K measurements, the 300 K results from Shawnam et al. [23] were used for the $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ derivation, which are consistent with other measurements. For experimental data, uncertainties in $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ were propagated from those of S_L and S_{L0} , as shown in Eq. (8). The obtained $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ values were analysed as functions of $(T_u - T_{u0}) / \ln(T_u/T_{u0}^0)$ and $X = (1/T_{ad0} - 1/T_{ad}) / \ln T_u - \ln T_{u0}$, corresponding to Eq. (5) and Eq. (3), respectively.

Fig. 1. Relationship of $\ln S_L$ vs. $\ln T_u$ for 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 +air flames at 1 atm with broad T_u range, where linear fitting results were presented with residuals. (a) $\phi = 0.8$, (b) $\phi = 1.0$, and (c) $\phi = 1.2$.

$$\Delta\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u} = \sqrt{(\Delta S_L/S_L)^2 + (\Delta S_{L0}/S_{L0})^2} / \ln(T_u/T_{u0}) \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2 shows the relationship between $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ and $(T_u - T_{u0}) / \ln(T_u/T_{u0})$ for 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 +air flames at 1 atm. Similar to Fig. 1, panels 2(a) to 2(c) correspond to $\phi = 0.8, 1.0$, and 1.2 , respectively, with the residuals from the linear fit of simulation results displayed at the top of each plot. From Fig. 2, the majority of $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ values derived from experimental data align with simulation results from various models within uncertainty ranges, reaffirming the validity of employing simulation results to determine the trend of $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$. The simulated $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ values increase approximately linearly with $(T_u - T_{u0}) / \ln(T_u/T_{u0})$, with $R^2 > 0.9961$. However, the residual, again, shows non-linearity at both ends of the curve, suggesting that the slope $1/T_{exp}$ in Eq. (5) is dependent on the temperature range under investigation. Given that the residuals from each model are negative at the curve's ends and positive in the middle, T_{exp} should increase with T_u . It is important to note that Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21] treated T_{exp} as well as α_{NA} as empirically fitted values independent of T_u or T_{u0} . However, the residuals in Fig. 2 suggest that the values provided in [21] are indeed the averaged values of T_{exp} and α_{NA} within their studied temperature range from 500 K to 800

K, and their accuracy may diminish when applied to other conditions.

Fig. 3 shows the relationship between $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ and X for 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 +air flames at 1 atm, plotted analogously to Fig. 2, with variations only in the x-axis data and linear fitting residuals. Similar to the findings in Fig. 2, the experimental data tendency of $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ vs. X is accurately represented by the simulation results, which exhibit strong linearity with an R^2 value exceeding 0.9929, irrespective of the model used and ϕ . The linear fitting residuals of the simulation results also suggest non-linearity at the extremes of the lines, being positive at both ends and negative in the middle, in contrast to the residuals of the $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ vs. $(T_u - T_{u0}) / \ln(T_u/T_{u0})$ linear fitting. According to Eq. (3), the slope of the $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ vs. X line is $E_a/2R$, reflecting the overall activation energy E_a if considering a global one-step reaction controlling the flame propagation. For the residual values in Fig. 3, E_a is anticipated to increase with T_u .

Comparing Figs. 2 and 3, the absolute fitting residuals for both $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ vs. $(T_u - T_{u0}) / \ln(T_u/T_{u0})$ and $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ vs. X peak at approximately 0.025, with the former being smaller than the latter for $\phi = 1.2$. This suggests that applying Eq. (5) with linear fittings of T_{exp} and α_{NA} likely yields more accurate S_L evaluations than Eq. (3) with E_a and x at

Fig. 2. Relationship of $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ vs. $(T_u - T_{u0}) / \ln(T_u/T_{u0})$ for 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 +air flames at 1 atm with broad T_u range, where linear fitting results were presented with residuals. (a) $\phi = 0.8$, (b) $\phi = 1.0$, and (c) $\phi = 1.2$.

Fig. 3. Relationship of $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ vs. X for 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 +air flames at 1 atm with broad T_u range, where linear fitting results were presented with residuals. (a) $\phi = 0.8$, (b) $\phi = 1.0$, and (c) $\phi = 1.2$.

the fuel-rich side, for a specific $T_{u0} - T_u$ range, thus should be preferred in practical use in engine calculations. However, it's important to note that obtaining accurate T_{exp} and α_{NA} values (also E_a and x) is difficult. For experiment, very-high temperature measurement should be carried out, which can't be achieved by traditional setups. For simulation, a specific model should be identified first, but with this model, direct simulation of S_L under the engine conditions yield more accurate results than using any of the correlations. How to more easily find an accurate model will be introduced in the following section, where Eq. (3) was used in the analysis because its fitted parameters have physical significance, reflecting the characteristics of the global one-step reaction that describes the overall flame kinetics.

Figs. 2 and 3 also reveal that the simulation spread from various models for $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ is much smaller than the corresponding experimental uncertainties for most conditions. Specifically, under each specific T_u , the maximum deviation of simulated $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ from the average value of the seven models is within 3.1%, 4.5%, and 5.2% at $\phi = 0.8, 1.0$, and 1.2, respectively. These values are generally far smaller than the experimental uncertainties ranging from 6.3%-223%, 4.2%-39.9%, and 6.4%-95.4% among the various experimental results shown. In contrast, the simulation scatter and experimental uncertainties of $\ln S_L$ in Fig. 1 are better comparable, as are those for S_L , where the maximum deviation from the averaged S_L value of the seven models are within 16% while the experimental uncertainties ranged from 1% to 14% under most conditions, except for two points from Lhuillier et al. [9] with significant uncertainties. These observations are consistent with previous findings that $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ shows less variety from different model

predictions than S_L , though obtained from the lower unburnt temperatures of <500 K of various fuels [15]. This feature will be explained by sensitivity analysis in the following section.

Fig. 4 shows the overall activation energies in the form of $E_a/2R$ for 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 +air flames at 1 atm as a function of T_u , which were derived from the $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ vs. X simulation results in Fig. 3. For a given T_u , E_a was derived using a series of $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ and X values with $T_u \pm 50$ K to mitigate numerical noise, as these calculations are based on the second-order differences of the calculated S_L . More specifically, the presented E_a values are averaged values within a 100 K temperature span. Due to noise concerns, E_a derivation from experimental data was not conducted, but the simulation results are considered sufficiently representative, as the experimental and simulated $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ values align well in both Figs. 2 and 3. In Fig. 4, the lines for $\phi = 1.0$ and 1.2 in panels (b) and (c) are smoother than those for $\phi = 0.8$ in panel (a), attributed to the lower laminar burning velocities at $\phi = 0.8$ making the derivation results more susceptible to numerical noise.

From Fig. 4, different models yield varying activation energies, E_a , under the same flame conditions, with differences among the models tested exceeding 30%. Despite these variations, it is evident that both E_a and its slope increase with T_u . For instance, from 350 K to 450 K, the increase in E_a across a 100 K interval is approximately 5%, whereas it rises to 30% for the interval from 750 K to 850 K. This observation may explain why previous studies assumed and confirmed E_a to be independent on T_u [8,11,20], as most of these studies were conducted within the T_u range of 300–500 K, where the increase in E_a was minor to be detected through linear fitting, even with residual analysis. It is only

Fig. 4. The averaged overall activation energy of 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 +air flames at 1 atm as a function of T_u . (a) $\phi = 0.8$, (b) $\phi = 1.0$, and (c) $\phi = 1.2$.

with the advent of high-temperature measurement techniques such as the shock tube spherical flame and externally heated diverging channel methods that measurements at very high temperatures have become feasible, validating model predictions and enabling analysis using low-noise simulation results.

4.2. Sensitivity analysis

To assess the behaviour of S_L and $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ as discussed in the previous section, A-factor reaction sensitivities were calculated. The sensitivity of the laminar burning velocity S_L for the i^{th} reaction in a model, denoted as $S_{S_L}^i$, is expressed as Eq. (9), where k_i represents the reaction rate constant. $S_{S_L}^i$ was directly extracted from the Chemkin software, which resolves the Jacobian matrix [27]. The A-factor sensitivity of $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ was derived using the sensitivity values of S_{L0} and S_L , as shown in Eq. (10) [35].

$$S_{S_L}^i = \frac{\partial \ln S_L}{\partial \ln k_i} \quad (9)$$

$$S_{\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}}^i = \frac{\partial \ln \alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}}{\partial \ln k_i} = \left(S_{S_L}^i - S_{S_{L0}}^i \right) / \ln \left(S_L / S_{L0}^0 \right) \quad (10)$$

Fig. 5 shows the A-factor reaction sensitivities for stoichiometric 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 flames at 1 atm and various unburnt temperatures, with panels (a) and (b) illustrating sensitivities for S_L and $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$, respectively. The results shown were calculated using the NUIG model, which is the most recently published among the tested models and is used as a representative example. Each panel in Fig. 5 includes the 15 most influential reactions, ranked by the sum of their absolute sensitivity values under the investigated conditions. The 15 dominant reactions for S_L , listed below, consist of 5 H/O reactions (R1-R5) and 10 N/H/O reactions (R6-R15), with reaction R3 exhibiting significantly larger absolute sensitivity values compared to others. These reactions are highlighted with red boxes on both panels.

From Fig. 5, the S_L sensitivity variations across the broad T_u range from 298 K to 898 K are not pronounced; the maximum S_L sensitivity difference is 0.073 for R3, far less than its sensitivity values of about 0.6. The limited sensitivity difference among various temperatures results in much lower $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ sensitivities in panel (b) compared to the S_L sensitivities in panel (a), where all absolute $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ sensitivity values were found less than 0.05, regardless of reactions and unburnt temperatures. Consequently, even with substantial rate constant uncertainties in any reactions, $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ should be less affected than S_L , enabling any model to reasonably reproduce $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ even with large differences in predicting S_L as originally discussed by Christensen et al. [35]. This kinetic rationale explains why the simulations scatter among various models for $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ in Figs. 2 and 3 is much smaller than the corresponding experimental uncertainties, in contrast to the comparable $\ln S_L$ simulation scatter and experimental uncertainties in Fig. 1.

Fig. 5. A-factor reaction sensitivities of S_L and $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ for stoichiometric 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 +air flames at 1 atm and various unburnt temperatures, calculated using the NUIG model. (a) S_L sensitivities and (b) $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ sensitivities.

It should be reminded that simulated $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ or averaged α values have long been used as criteria to assess the reliability and data consistency of experimental S_L data in previous studies with T_u below 500 K [8,15]. Essentially, if experimental $\alpha \pm \Delta\alpha$ significantly deviates from simulation results, the S_L experimental uncertainties are considered to be larger than reported. With the current findings, $\alpha_{T_{u0} \rightarrow T_u}$ or averaged α can also be applied for data consistency analysis including $T_u > 800$ K

conditions, helping to identify more reliable datasets. Considering the comparisons in Figs. 2 and 3, all tested experimental data align with at least one of the model predictions, thus no inconsistencies were identified.

To check if the same effects of elevated temperature and oxygen enrichment on model validations as well as similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities found in [26] are also valid for higher temperatures, reaction sensitivities with different oxygen enrichment ratios were also calculated. Fig. 6 shows the S_L reaction sensitivities of the 15 most dominant reactions for stoichiometric 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 flames at 1 atm, 298 K, and various oxygen enrichment ratios. The oxygen enrichment ratio is described using the parameter x_{O_2} , which represents the mole fraction of O_2 in the O_2+N_2 mixture; for example, $x_{O_2} = 0.21$ corresponds to the ambient air. In Fig. 6, reactions enclosed in red boxes are the same as those observed under various T_u conditions in Fig. 5(a). The reactions in Figs 6 and 5(a) are indeed identical, with similar reaction sensitivity values, although the order of reactions varies slightly. This observation suggests that altering any sensitive reaction will concurrently modify the S_L vs. x_{O_2} and S_L vs. T_u predictions at the same time in the same direction. It is also observed that the range of x_{O_2} variations in Fig. 6 generally leads to larger reaction sensitivity differences than those of T_u variations Fig. 5(a). For example, the maximum S_L sensitivity difference for R3 is 0.134 in Fig. 6, from $x_{O_2} = 0.21 \sim 0.33$, almost twice as much as that in Fig. 5(a). This finding aligns with investigations at T_u below 500 K [26]. The identical dominant reactions with similar reaction sensitivity values for T_u and x_{O_2} variations were also found for other model tested, which can be found in Fig. S1 in the Supplementary Material. Moreover, this finding is consistent across broad equivalence ratio conditions (0.4–1.7), broad pressure conditions (0.5–10 atm), and broad fuel mixture composition conditions (from 100% NH_3 +0% H_2 to 0% NH_3 +100% H_2), which can be found in Fig. S2-S4 in the Supplementary Material. However, it is also noted that the dominant reactions and sensitivity values differ across various models, indicating that the model improvements regarding the very-high T_u laminar burning velocities is model-dependent, which will be discussed in the following Section 4.3.

Fig. 7 shows the areas for stoichiometric 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 flames at 1 atm that have nearly identical S_L reaction sensitivity values for all

Fig. 6. A-factor S_L reaction sensitivities of stoichiometric 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 flames at 1 atm, 298 K, and various oxygen enrichment ratios, calculated using the NUIG model.

Fig. 7. Similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities of stoichiometric 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 flames at 1 atm, with contour lines of overall activation energy for the global one-step reaction. Calculations using the (a) Han model, (b) Stagni model, and (c) NUIG model.

reactions in a model in each of them, confirming the existence of similar flame conditions in terms of reaction sensitivities under high- T_u conditions. The results from the Han, Stagni, and NUIG models are displayed in panels (a), (b), and (c), respectively. In each panel, the x- and y-axes represent the investigated ranges of x_{O_2} and T_u , which are 0.21 – 0.35 and 350 K – 850 K, respectively. The center points of the colored areas are (0.23, 573 K), (0.27, 598 K), and (0.31, 689 K), selected for presentation purposes to ensure even distribution across the plot without overlap. Numerous other similar-condition areas exist but are not

shown; these can be deemed parallel to the displayed areas. From panels (a-c), the similar conditions identified by different models are largely consistent, indicating that the similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities observed are not merely coincidental outcomes arising from limited investigation ranges or the utilization of specific models. It should be noted that the O_2 enrichment affects the reaction kinetics through third-body reactions and transport properties, and the observed consistent $x_{O_2} - T_u$ similarities across different models (also seen in Fig. S1) could be due to the limited x_{O_2} change in the found similar conditions areas weakens these effects.

In Figs. 7(a-c), for each center point, sensitivity difference criteria levels from ± 0.003 to ± 0.009 for each center point are indicated by different colors (the readers are referred to the web version to check the colors more clearly). Within the ± 0.003 criterion area, for instance, every condition has a maximum ± 0.003 difference from the center point condition in their S_L sensitivity values for each reaction in the model. Due to the small sensitivity differences, modifying any reaction will alter all S_L at the similar conditions with a nearly identical ratio. For example, if the A-factor of a single reaction i increases by 100%, leading to approximately $S_{S_L}^i \times 100\%$ relative change in the center point S_L according to Eq. (9), then the S_L change at the similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities by this modification will be less than $S_{S_L}^i \pm 0.003$, $S_{S_L}^i \pm 0.006$, and $S_{S_L}^i \pm 0.009$, corresponding to different criteria adopted. Considering the absolute S_L sensitivities of ~ 0.05 – 0.65 for the dominant reactions shown in Fig. 5, all these criteria were considered strict, making any model accurately predicting one flame condition within the area tends to replicate all other conditions well. Therefore, consistent with the conclusion reached under the $T_u < 500$ K conditions [26], the S_L measurements with very-high T_u (e.g., condition I with $x_{O_2} = 0.22$, $T_u = 700$ K) could be substituted by the measurements with elevated oxygen enrichment ratios but lower T_u (e.g. condition combination II with $x_{O_2} = 0.24$, $T_u = 400$ K from the 0.009 criterion), which have the same effect in identifying a more accurate model. Compared with the measurements at very high temperatures, the oxygen enriched experiments are easier to carry out. Most importantly, there is no need to consider the equipment heat resistance or fuel pre-decomposition related to very high T_u , instead, the oxygen enriched conditions can be achieved by only adjusting the mass flow controllers, e.g., increasing the O_2 concentration in the unburnt mixture from $x_{O_2} = 0.22$ to $x_{O_2} = 0.24$ for the condition combinations I and II. However, the following cautions should also be taken when using this substitution.

- (1) Similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities depend on adopted similarity criteria (e.g., 0.009), which is model-specific. Since the sensitivity criteria affect S_L differences via rate constant uncertainties, it's suggested to evaluate uncertainties in key reactions before selecting a similarity threshold to avoid overly strict standards. For example, if a key reaction's rate constant has 10% uncertainty, a criterion like 0.009 is sufficiently strict, producing a negligible $\sim 0.09\%$ difference ($0.009 \times 10\%$ via Eq. (9)) in the S_L ratio between any identified similar flame conditions. In this situation, the substitution of condition combination II to condition combination I can reduce the unburnt temperature by 300 K. In contrast, if uncertainty is 1000%, the same criterion causes a significant $\sim 9\%$ difference, requiring stricter criteria with less unburnt temperature reduction.
- (2) Lowering the unburnt temperature drastically reduces laminar burning velocity, which even increased oxygen levels cannot offset. This imbalance, together with potential thermal-diffusive instabilities from increased amounts of O_2 , must be addressed in experiments using substituted similar conditions to avoid risks like flashback.

Figs. 7(a-c) also show the contour lines of the overall activation

energy calculated using each model, explaining the similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities from the perspective of a global one-step reaction. The calculation method is the same as that in Fig. 4, i. e., linear fitting the $\alpha_{T_u0 \rightarrow T_u}$ vs. T values within a 100 K T_u interval, with the fitted slope being $E_a/2R$ according to Eq. (3). It should be recalled that the E_a can also be written in a more generalized form as $E_a/2R = -\frac{\partial \ln(\rho_u S_L)}{\partial(1/T_{ad})} |_P$, where P denotes a given pressure and T_{ad} is the adiabatic flame temperature [36]. Thus, the A-factor reaction sensitivity for E_a from the i^{th} reaction in model can be written as Eq. (11), directly correlated to the S_L sensitivity $S_{S_L}^i$. Eq. (11) reveals that the differences in the E_a prediction from different models, e.g., in Figs. 4 and 7(a-c), are due to their differences in predicting S_L with various unburnt temperatures (corresponding to the modification in T_{ad} in Eq. (11)). If similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities are also characterized by nearly identical adiabatic flame temperature T_{ad} , then the same E_a should be expected according to Eq. (11). However, variations were found in T_{ad} within the areas of similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities [26], corresponding to the variations in the E_a values within each of the areas shown in Fig. 7. From this perspective, the similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities are a specific feature of flames, which is connected with but not solely dependent on the global flame characteristics such as T_{ad} and E_a .

$$S_{E_a}^i = \frac{\partial \ln E_a}{\partial \ln k_i} = \frac{2R}{E_a} \frac{\partial(\partial \ln(\rho_u S_L) / \partial(1/T_{ad}))}{\partial \ln k_i} = \frac{2R}{E_a} \frac{\partial(\partial \ln(\rho_u S_L) / \partial \ln k_i)}{\partial(1/T_{ad})} = \frac{2R}{E_a} \frac{\partial(S_{S_L}^i)}{\partial(1/T_{ad})} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 8 shows the E_a reaction sensitivities of the 15 most dominant reactions for stoichiometric $40\%H_2 + 60\%NH_3 + \text{air}$ flames at 1 atm, 298 K and 898 K, calculated using the NUIG model. The results were derived from the S_L sensitivities using Eq. (11), where small T_{ad} variations allowed the partial derivative to be approximated by a finite difference. Compared with S_L and α sensitivities in Fig. 5, many differences can be found in the E_a sensitivities. The reactions $NH_3 + OH = H_2O + NH_2$ and $H + NH_2 = H_2 + NH$, which exhibit negligible sensitivity for S_L and α , have noticeable sensitivity values for E_a . Additionally, E_a sensitivities display stronger temperature dependence, e.g., for reaction R3, absolute

Fig. 8. A-factor E_a reaction sensitivities in stoichiometric $40\%H_2 + 60\%NH_3 + \text{air}$ flames at 1 atm, 298 K and 898 K, calculated using the NUIG model.

sensitivity values decrease by 15% for S_L , 35% for α , and 75% for E_a from 298 K to 898 K. These differences make E_a sensitivities more effective than S_L or α for identifying reactions requiring adjustment for improving predictions across wide unburnt temperature ranges. The stronger temperature dependence of E_a sensitivities were also found for the other models, and the results can be found Fig. S5 in the Supplementary Material. It is also noted from Figs. 8 and S5 that though the dominant reactions and their sensitivity values are different across various models, the E_a sensitivities for reactions $\text{H}_2+\text{OH}=\text{H}+\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (R2) and $\text{NH}_3+\text{OH}=\text{NH}_2+\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are featured with noticeable dependence on unburnt temperature, where more than 90% change from 298 K to 898 K was found. Thus, model updates targeting broad T_u ranges should prioritize these reactions, while also considering the sensitivity spectrum of individual models and their alignment with experimental data.

Based on the findings above, the following strategy was proposed for future investigations of the laminar burning velocities with broad unburnt temperature range:

- (1) To obtain accurate experimental S_L data by substituting the direct measurement with very high T_u by that of a similar flame condition with lower T_u and higher x_{O_2} . The rate constant uncertainty of the S_L -dominant reactions and flame instabilities in the substituted flame condition need to be considered, as detailed above.
- (2) To validate or update a kinetic model based on the experimental S_L data. For the model update, the E_a sensitivities more effective than S_L or α for identifying reactions requiring adjustment for improving predictions across wide unburnt temperature ranges, and reactions $\text{H}_2+\text{OH}=\text{H}+\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (R2) and $\text{NH}_3+\text{OH}=\text{NH}_2+\text{H}_2\text{O}$ should receive special attention.
- (3) With an accurate model, simulations could be carried out to analyse the kinetic behaviour or the laminar burning velocity data. For the latter purpose, besides the direct S_L simulations, the $\alpha_{T_{u0}-T_u}$ or averaged α values as well as the fitting parameters in Eqs. (3) and (5) can also be calculated based on limited simulation results, and then help to interpolate or extrapolate S_L under other conditions, thus saving the simulation time.

5. Conclusions

In this work, the relationship between the NH_3 laminar burning velocities S_L and unburnt mixture temperature T_u was investigated across a large T_u span, from 298 K to above 800 K, through the analysis of literature experimental data and simulation results. The 40% H_2 +60% NH_3 +air flames at 1 atm were selected for analysis, representing the only available literature measurements with $T_u > 500$ K conditions, as reported by Figueroa-Labastida et al. [21] and Shawnam et al. [23]. Seven kinetic models were adopted in the simulations, and those from Shrestha, Stagni, Han, NUIG, and KAUST well reproduce the experimental S_L data within uncertainties. The analysis of simulation results revealed that none of the correlations in Eqs. (1)(3)(4) could perfectly capture the S_L vs. T_u dependence across the entire investigated T_u range with their originally defined constants. The α in Eq. (1) increases with T_u , consistent with both our previous findings [8,11,20] and those from [21,22,24,25], while different from these investigations, the E_a and x in Eq. (3) as well as α_{NA} and T_{exp} in Eq. (4) were all found dependent on T_u .

Besides the correlations, the same effects of elevated temperature and oxygen enrichment for model validations, as well as similar flame conditions with nearly identical sensitivities demonstrated in [26], were found to be valid for higher temperatures up to 850 K in the current simulations. Based on these observations, a strategy was proposed to facilitate the acquisition of very high- T_u laminar burning velocities necessary for practical applications. Specifically, S_L measurements with very high- T_u could be replaced by measurements with elevated oxygen enrichment ratios at lower T_u , which are easier to implement in experiments and equally effective in identifying a more accurate kinetic

model. Model updating could also be carried out using these data, where the E_a sensitivities are more effective than S_L or α for identifying reactions requiring adjustment across wide unburnt temperature ranges. With a selected model, simulations could be conducted to calculate the S_L directly, also, α values as well as the E_a and x or α_{NA} and T_{exp} can be fitted with limited S_L data and then interpolated or extrapolated to obtain S_L under other conditions to save the simulation time.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Xinlu Han: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alexander A. Konnov:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.combustflame.2025.114117.

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